

Green synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones[†]

Renuka Jain^{*a}, Kanti Sharma^b and Deepak Kumar^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : profrajain@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, R. L. Saharia Govt. P.G. College, Kaladera, Jaipur-303 801, Rajasthan, India

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Abstract : A green and facile protocol for the synthesis of novel 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones by the reaction of 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole in [bmim]PF₆ (1-butyl-3-methyl-1H-imidazolium hexafluorophosphate) as a recyclable ionic liquid solvent gave good to excellent yields. Analytical and spectral (IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and mass) techniques were employed for the structural elucidation of the synthesized compounds. Further, on evaluation of antimicrobial activity almost all the synthesized compounds exhibited significant effect.

Keywords : Spiro[indole-pyrazole], ionic liquid, antimicrobial activity, environmentally benign approach.

Introduction

In this century, one of the challenges faced by chemists is to develop new transformations that are not only efficient, selective and high yielding but also environmentally as well as economically benign. During the last decade, the topic of 'green chemistry' has received increasing attention which aims in the development of cleaner and more benign chemical processes by replacement of volatile and hazardous reagents and solvents with environmentally benign materials and thus increase the process selectivity¹⁻³. In this regard, ionic liquids (ILs) have frequently been used as alternative reaction media for a wide range of chemical transformations or modifications and are emerging as a set of new green solvents to replace the volatile organic solvents^{4,5}. The utilization of non-volatile organic solvents for chemical reactions is of ecological and economic importance. These are interesting materials for chemists as they offer new robust chemical and physical properties such as low volatility, high thermal and chemical stability, very low to negligible vapour pressure, good solvating ability, non-coordinating nature and the potential for recycling and compatibi-

lity with various organic compounds and organometallic catalysts. In recent years, ionic liquids have concerned increasing interest as recyclable solvents, catalysts and reagents owing to their green credentials and tunable properties^{6,7}.

Progress in the development of new antimicrobial agents with new structure along with mode of action remains the main purpose of scientists for the solution of growing bacterial resistance gained by micro-organisms to classical antimicrobial agents⁸. Indole-2,3-dione (isatin) and its derivatives are versatile starting materials for the construction of highly functionalized molecules with significant biological activities⁹. The compounds possessing this heterocyclic nucleus have been isolated from plants also¹⁰. Furthermore, those compounds in which indole-3-carbon is in the form of a spiro atom exhibit enhanced bioactivity¹¹⁻¹³. A number of natural products possessing significant biological activity contain a spiro-oxindole moiety (Fig. 1).

Besides indoles, benzothiazole and its derivatives^{14,15} have also been recognized as a class of medicinal importance. These represent an extensive group of heterocyclic

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Fig. 1. Examples of spiro-oxindoles found in natural products.

compounds, several of which have already found application in the medical sphere¹⁶ as well as in agriculture¹⁷. Many substituted benzothiazoles are known to possess antituberculosic¹⁸, antibacterial and antifungal activities^{19,20} and are also reported to be active as antineoplastic agents²¹.

Studies reveal that incorporation of pyrazole moiety into various heterocyclic ring systems gives worthwhile molecules from the biological point of view^{22–24}. The construction of pyrazolines has engrossed significant interest from organic and medicinal chemists because of their use as analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, hypoglycemic, sedative-hypnotic, antitumor and anticoagulant agents^{25–28}. Also, a wide spectrum of pharmacological activities are associated with pyrazole derivatives when present along with indole nucleus²⁹.

Chalcones, being highly reactive synthones, are an attractive molecular scaffold for the search of new biologically active molecules. Isatin chalcone, 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-one is still more reactive as it contains a double bond flanked by carbonyl group on both sides. The reaction of this nucleus with various amino compounds viz. hydrazines³⁰, thiosemicarbazide³¹ and hydrazinobenzimidazole³² have been previously investigated by us but the reaction with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole has not been studied so far and also there is no report on the synthesis of spiro[indole-pyrazoles] in ionic liquid previously. Therefore, it appeared to be of interest to develop eco-friendly, facile and more practical procedure for the synthesis of spiro[indole-pyrazole] derivatives in-

corporating a benzothiazole moiety.

In continuation of our search for better and improved bioactive heterocycles^{33–37}, we have synthesized a series of novel 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones by the reaction of 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole using [bmim]PF₆, as a recyclable ionic-liquid solvent with the assumption that the incorporation of more than one bioactive heterocyclic moiety into a single framework may result into the construction of novel heterocycles with improved bioactivity.

Results and discussion

The present report describes the synthesis of a series of novel 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (**3a-h**) by the reaction of 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones (**1a-h**) and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (**2**) in [bmim]PF₆, an ionic liquid as a recyclable as well as greener solvent in excellent yields (Scheme 1).

The selection of an appropriate reaction condition is of essential importance for successful synthesis. In our preliminary investigation, the reactions of 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones (**1a-b**) and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (**2**), as model reactions, were investigated to establish the feasibility of the strategy and optimize the reaction conditions. Various solvents such as ethanol (neutral/acidic/basic), acetic acid and [bmim]PF₆, an ionic liquid were screened and the best results were obtained in [bmim]PF₆ with excellent yield in shorter reaction time where there was no requirement for a further purification process like column chromatography.

As in our earlier published work³⁸, it was found that this reaction offers three different possibilities (Scheme 2) viz. formation of 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-one (**3**), 3-benzoyl(2-benzothiazolyl)hydrazonemethylene-indol-2(1*H*)-one (**4**) and 3-benzothiazolyl-1-phenyl-9*H*-pyridazino[3,4-*b*]indole (**5**) depending on the site of condensation. The products formed depend on the nature of solvent, medium and substitution on indolyl nitrogen. With simple 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-one, the reaction gave only **3** in [bmim]PF₆, an ionic liquid, while it gave a mixture containing **3** and **4** in neutral and slightly acidic medium. In basic medium (ethanol with few drops of

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Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones (**3a-h**).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of compounds **3a-b**, **4a-b** and **5a**.

diethylamine) and pure acetic acid this reaction affords a mixture of **3**, **4** and **5**. In the case of methyl substituted indolyl nitrogen, ionic liquid, neutral and basic medium afford only the product **3** while in acidic medium and pure acetic acid mixture of products viz. **3** and **4** were obtained. Our results indicate that when indolyl nitrogen is substituted then **5** was not formed at all.

The synthesis of title compounds (**3a-h**) has been performed by taking 3-arylmethyleneindol-2-ones (**1a-h**,

1.0 mmol) and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (**2**, 1.0 mmol) in ionic liquid, [bmim]PF₆. The reactions have been carried out by stirring the reaction mixture under N₂ atmosphere at 80 ± 2 °C until completion of the reaction as evidenced by TLC (Scheme 1).

The formation of products (**3**, **4** and **5**) can be explained as follows : The reactions were carried out in different reaction media and found that in acidic, basic and neutral medium, the reaction resulted in the forma-

tion of hydrazone (**4**), which under certain conditions, when R=H can react with the enolic form eliminating water molecule to give the condensed product i.e. pyridazino derivative (**5a**). Alternatively, nucleophilic Michael addition of **2** to the **1** gives rise to spiro[indole-pyrazole] (**3**).

In the IR spectrum of **3a**, absorption bands at 3400 and 3290 cm^{-1} due to $>\text{NH}$ of indolinone and pyrazole, respectively and at 1680 cm^{-1} due to $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ of indole are observed. In its ^1H NMR spectrum, signals appeared at δ 6.25 due to pyrazolyl $=\text{CH}-$, δ 9.81 for $>\text{NH}$ of indole ring and δ 6.87–8.25 due to aromatic protons. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum exhibited peaks at δ 191.2 and 128.6 due to $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ (indole ring) and $=\text{CH}-$ (pyrazolyl ring), respectively. The signal at δ 110.4 indicated the presence of a quaternary carbon atom with spiro linkage. The structure was further confirmed by mass spectrum, where molecular ion peak appeared at m/z 396.4 [M^+] corresponding to the molecular mass of product **3a**.

The recyclability of the regenerated ionic liquid for the product **3a** was also studied (Table 1). The yield of the product indicate a decrease in various cycles, however the ionic liquid can be reused with significant success. Hence, this protocol is advantageous over the conventional reaction media.

Table 1. Studies on the recyclability of [bmim]PF₆ for **3a**^a

Sr. no.	Compd.	Run	Yield ^b (%)	Time (h)	IL recovered (w/w %)
1.	3a	Fresh	85	5	97
2.	3a	1	82	5	95
3.	3a	2	80	5	92

^aReaction conditions : 0.01 mol of **1a** and **2**, respectively; 5.0 mL of ionic liquid (IL) was used for the first run.

^bYields of product.

Antimicrobial activity :

The synthesized 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1H)-one derivatives (**3a-h**) were subjected to *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against various plant and human pathogenic bacteria and fungi and results are summarized in the Tables 2 and 3 for antibacterial and antifungal, respectively.

The investigation of antibacterial screening data revealed that all the tested compounds (**3a-h**) showed mod-

erate to significant bacterial inhibition (Table 2). Compounds **3e** and **3f** are more potent than gentamycin (standard) against *Raoultella planticola* and *Bacillus subtilis* bacterial strains respectively. Compounds **3a**, **3e** and **3g** exhibited better activity against *B. subtilis*; **3c**, **3e**, **3f**, **3g** and **3h** showed better results against *Escherichia coli*; **3a**, **3f** and **3g** exhibited better activity against *R. planticola* and compounds **3f** and **3g** exhibited better results against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

The antifungal screening data of the compounds revealed good to moderate activity (Table 3). Compounds **3d**, **3e** and **3f** exhibited even better inhibitory activity against tested fungi, *Aspergillus flavus* as compared to ketoconazole as standard. Also, compounds **3a** and **3h** showed more potent antifungal activity nearly equivalent to that of standard against *A. flavus*. Compounds **3b**, **3c** and **3g** exhibited moderate activity against *A. flavus* while **3d** and **3f** also showed good activity against *A. niger*. None of the compounds was found to be active against *Candida albicans*.

Conclusions

A convenient, efficient and environmentally benign synthesis of a series of novel 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones has been accomplished by the reaction of 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole using ionic liquid for the first time. The recyclability of ionic liquid as well as absence of catalyst makes this procedure, cleaner and promising for scale up. The advantages of this protocol over conventional methods are the mild reaction conditions, the high products yields in shorter reaction time as well as the eco-friendly conditions. Further, the synthesized compounds (**3a-h**) were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity and the data revealed that some compounds were even more active than the standard and could act as potential antimicrobial agents.

Experimental

Material, methods and instruments :

Melting points were determined in open end capillaries using Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on an 8400S SHIMADZU IR spectrometer using KBr pellets and band positions were recorded in wave numbers (cm^{-1}). ^1H and

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (**3a-h**)

Compd.	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>R. planticola</i>		<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	
	IZ	AI	IZ	AI	IZ	AI	IZ	AI	IZ	AI
3a	18.33	0.83	13.66	0.65	14.33	0.75	17.33	0.82	17.33	0.72
3b	17.33	0.79	14.66	0.70	13.66	0.72	14.66	0.69	18.66	0.77
3c	15.66	0.71	11.00	0.52	15.66	0.82	13.33	0.63	14.66	0.61
3d	17.33	0.79	13.33	0.63	12.33	0.65	15.66	0.74	17.33	0.72
3e	19.66	0.89	14.00	0.67	17.00	0.89	22.00	1.04	19.00	0.79
3f	24.33	1.11	16.33	0.78	18.00	0.95	18.33	0.87	22.66	0.94
3g	19.66	0.89	15.00	0.71	15.33	0.81	18.00	0.85	21.00	0.88
3h	17.33	0.79	12.66	0.60	16.66	0.87	15.00	0.71	15.00	0.62

IZ = Inhibition zone (in mm) including the diameter of disc (6 mm, mean); AI = Activity index = Inhibition zone of sample/Inhibition zone of standard; Standard : Gentamycin.

Table 3. Antifungal activity of 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (**3a-h**)

Compd.	<i>A. flavus</i>		<i>A. niger</i>		<i>C. albicans</i>	
	IZ	AI	IZ	AI	IZ	AI
3a	15.33	0.96	12.33	0.68	12.66	0.57
3b	14.66	0.92	13.66	0.76	14.33	0.65
3c	13.66	0.85	11.00	0.61	12.33	0.56
3d	18.33	1.14	16.66	0.92	11.66	0.53
3e	17.66	1.10	13.33	0.74	12.00	0.54
3f	18.00	1.12	14.66	0.81	14.00	0.64
3g	14.00	0.87	13.00	0.72	12.00	0.54
3h	15.66	0.97	12.66	0.70	12.33	0.56

IZ = Inhibition zone (in mm) including the diameter of disc (6 mm); AI = Activity index = Inhibition zone of sample/Inhibition zone of standard; Standard : Ketoconazole.

¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆/CDCl₃ with TMS as an internal reference on a JEOL spectrometer at 300 and 75 MHz, respectively. The purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel plate using benzene and ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as eluent and spots were located by iodine vapors. The [bmim]PF₆, an ionic liquid was purchased from Acros Organics. 3-Aroylmethylene-indol-2-ones (**1a-h**) were prepared according to literature method³⁹ and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (**2**) by the method of Sharma *et al.*⁴⁰.

Preparation of 1'-benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones (3) :

A mixture of **1a-h** (0.01 mol), **2** (0.01 mol) and [bmim]PF₆, an ionic liquid (5.0 mL) was taken in a round bottom flask without catalyst and solution was stirred magnetically for 4–5 h at 80 ± 2 °C under nitrogen

atmosphere. After completion of reaction as evidenced by TLC, the reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature and contents were neutralized by 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 10 mL). The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The pasty mass, thus obtained was extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 10 mL), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, ether distilled off and the obtained crude mixture of products was purified by crystallization with ethanol to yield spiro products (**3a-h**). The ionic liquid layer was washed with water (3 × 10 mL) and kept for 2 h at 80 °C under reduced pressure. This ionic liquid was used in recycling.

1'-Benzothiazolo-5'-phenyl-2',4'-dihydrospiro[indole-3,3'-pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (3a) : m.p. 268–270 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₆N₄OS : C, 69.69; H, 4.04; N, 14.14 (%). Found : C, 69.76; H, 4.15; N, 14.03 (%); IR (KBr) : 3400 (>NH of indole), 3290 (NH of pyrazole), 1680 (>C=O); ¹H NMR (δ) ppm : 6.25 (1H, s, =CH- of pyrazole), 7.73 (1H, s, -NH of pyrazole), 6.87–8.25 (13H, m, Ar-H), 9.81 (1H, s, >NH of indole); ¹³C NMR (δ) ppm : 110.4 (spiro carbon), 118.2–137.5 (aromatic carbons), 128.6 (=CH- of pyrazole), 144.7 (C=N), 191.2 (>C=O); MS (*m/z*) : 396.4 [M⁺].

The analytical and spectral data of the synthesized compounds (**3a-h**) are presented in Tables 4 and 5, respectively.

Antimicrobial assay :

Material and methods :

Source of test organisms : Bacteria : Pure cultures of test bacteria, namely Gram +ve : *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC

Table 4. Physical and analytical data of the compounds (**3a-h**)

Compd.	R	X	Y	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Time (h)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)		
							C	H	N
3a	H	H	H	268–270	85	5	69.69 (69.76)	4.04 (4.15)	14.14 (14.03)
3b	Me	H	H	292–294	87	5	70.24 (70.35)	4.39 (4.22)	13.66 (13.61)
3c	CH ₂ Ph	H	H	262–264	84	4	74.05 (74.11)	4.56 (4.49)	11.51 (11.58)
3d	H	Cl	H	182–184	86	5	64.11 (64.03)	3.51 (3.59)	13.01 (12.97)
3e	H	F	H	191–193	84	6	66.65 (66.73)	3.65 (3.51)	13.52 (13.57)
3f	H	H	4-F	164–166	83	5	66.65 (66.71)	3.65 (3.53)	13.52 (13.61)
3g	H	H	3-OMe	212–214	87	5	67.59 (67.66)	4.25 (4.18)	13.14 (13.17)
3h	CH ₂ Ph	H	4-F	236–238	82	4	71.41 (71.48)	4.19 (4.13)	11.11 (11.18)

Table 5. IR and ¹H NMR spectral data of the compounds (**3a-h**)

Sr. no.	Compd	IR (KBr, cm ⁻¹)			¹ H NMR (δ, ppm)				
		C=O	-NH		=CH-	-NH (pyrazolyl)	Ar-H	-NH (indolyl)	Other peaks
1.	3a	1680	3290	3400	6.25	7.73	6.87–8.25	9.81	-
2.	3b	1690	3280	-	6.19	7.85	6.69–8.21	-	3.48 (>NMe)
3.	3c	1690	3310	-	6.22	7.77	6.83–8.18	-	4.52 (>NCH ₂ -)
4.	3d	1685	3290	3390	6.27	7.65	6.78–7.99	9.92	-
5.	3e	1680	3300	3370	6.11	7.81	6.69–8.35	9.87	-
6.	3f	1690	3310	3410	6.25	7.72	6.73–8.04	9.97	-
7.	3g	1680	3290	3390	6.19	7.83	6.79–8.18	9.83	4.11 (-OMe)
8.	3h	1670	3310	-	6.17	7.69	6.85–8.01	-	4.59 (>NCH ₂ -)

441), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 740) and Gram -ve : *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 443), *Raoultella planticola* (MTCC 530), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (MTCC 109) were obtained from IMTECH, Chandigarh, India. These cultures were grown and maintained on Nutrient Broth medium (NBM) at 27 °C for 48 h.

Fungi : Pure cultures of test fungi namely *Aspergillus flavus* (ATCC 16870), *A. niger* (ATCC 322) and *Candida albicans* (ATCC 4718) were obtained from IARI, New Delhi, India, were cultured on Sabouraud Dextrose Broth (SDB) at 37 °C for 48 h.

Cultures of test microbes :

Stock cultures were maintained at 4 °C on slopes of nutrient agar. Active cultures for experiments were prepared by transferring an inoculating loop of cultures from the stock cultures to test tubes of NB medium for bacteria and SD broth for fungi which were incubated without agitation of 24 h at 37 °C and 25 °C, respectively.

Antibacterial and antifungal assay :

For both antibacterial and antifungal assay, agar well

diffusion method⁴¹ was adopted, because of its re-productivity and precision. The plates were prepared by pouring 15.0 mL of molten media into sterile petri plates. The plates were allowed to solidify for 5 min. Thereafter, 40 μL (in case of bacteria) and 80 μL (in case of fungi) suspension was spread uniformly with the help of a sterile glass spreader and dried for 5 min. The zone of inhibition were measured around sterilized dried well, which were containing 4 mg/well of the test compounds and control (gentamycin for bacteria and ketoconazole for fungi) as reference drugs separately. Such treated well were air-dried at room temperature, to remove any residual solvent which might interfere with the determination, sterilized and inoculated. Before incubation, these plates were placed at low temperature for 1 h so as to allow maximum diffusion of the compound from the test discs into the agar plate and later, these were kept for incubation at 37 °C for 24 h in case of bacteria and 36 h for fungi. At the end of incubation, inhibition zones formed around the well were measured with a transparent scale in millimeters. The experiments were performed in trip-

licate and the mean values of the diameter of inhibition were taken.

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